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Abstract:

In the last few years, India has built up a strong start-up ecosystem with new organizations taking birth every day. India is an emerging market for start-ups with its young and inspired pool of entrepreneurs. The whole ecosystem is continuously evolving and becoming more vibrant by incorporating emerging technologies in their solutions. Despite the rising popularity of start-ups, new businesses are facing some key challenges that are very difficult to conquer. Without overcoming these challenges start-ups cannot convert themselves into bigger businesses. Major problems which are troubling most start-ups are lack of clear understanding of policies, lack of funds, infrastructure, and experience in making good decisions, poor employee engagement and lack of guidance from experts. Although new initiatives taken by both state and central government are supporting and addressing some of these challenges, entrepreneurs must commit to addressing all other issues to sustain and grow in today's competitive market. This study attempts to explain the present scenario of start-up ecosystem in India and major challenges faced by these start-ups with real case examples.

Keywords: Start-up, ecosystem, entrepreneurs, challenges, policies, employee engagement

Objective:

The study is based on the secondary data which has been collected through websites, newspapers, magazines, government reports, books, and research papers. This research is focused on the following objectives:

1. To understand the present start-up ecosystem in India
2. To study the various policies, programs, agencies involved in enhancing the start-ups
3. To understand the various challenges faced by start-ups in India
4. To analyse various challenges faced by today's start-ups in India

Introduction:

The start-up ecosystem can be described as young, innovative and futuristic. Start-up companies are newly established companies or ventures that are in their initial stage of development. These types of companies are mainly associated with innovative technology-related projects, development, and distribution of new products processes and services.

Fig1: Start-up ecosystem

A start-up ecosystem mainly consists entrepreneurs with new business ideas, investors investing in new business ideas, other non-financial systems (incubators, accelerators), and academic institutes across the country, and central and state government with policies and programs supporting emerging start-ups.

Start-ups play an important role in the development and growth of the country. Since last few years, entrepreneurship and start-ups have become a phenomenon in this country. It is only in the last decade and a half that more people are thinking about creating jobs rather than searching for jobs. However, entering into start-up ecosystem and sustaining in today's competitive environment is tough as we see more failures than success. So it is very important for start-ups to be prepared to face all the challenges and hurdles in all stages of the development.

According to a survey conducted by NASSCOM and Zinnov research team, India is in the process of emerging as the third largest tech start-up destination in the world supported by some of the successful start-ups stories such as OLA Cabs, Paytm, and Urban Ladder. These successful start-ups have created a positive energy in the country encouraging the growth of many other start-ups.

India Start-up landscape 2017:

Fig2: India start-up landscape 2017

India continues to be one of the most attractive landscapes for start-ups. Over 1000 tech start-ups were added to make the total number of tech start-ups cross 5000. India has witnessed a strong growth in the B2B tech start-up landscape, focused on verticals such as e-commerce, health-tech, and fin-tech.

Among all the start-up hubs across India, cities such as Bangalore, Mumbai and Delhi/NCR have managed to attract more number of start-ups.

Programs, policies, and agencies for enhancing the start-up ecosystem in India

With the formation of the new Indian government in 2014, the start-up ecosystem in the country was invigorated by a slew of initiatives and programs undertaken by the incoming government. Currently, there are more than 50 active GOI policies to support the start-up ecosystem.

The most crucial initiative launched by the GOI was the Start-up India initiative. The “Start-up India Action Plan” was launched by the GOI on January 2016, in a bid to empower the burgeoning start-up movement in India. This action plan has readily simplified the start-up recognition as well as the tax benefit process. In addition, it has streamlined the entire funding, procurement, and the incubation processes. A “Funds of Funds” of Rs 10,000 crore was created as a part of this initiative for easy access to funding, which is managed by SIDBI. Some of the key features of the Start-up India initiative are as follows:

- Tax exemption pertaining to capital gains tax and income tax
- Credit guarantee trust
- \$1.5 billion in corpus over 4 years as a funding instrument
- Atal innovation mission
- Create above 30 incubators and innovation centres
- Setup 7 research parks and 5 biotech clusters
- Easy registration and recognition
- Legal support
- Simple procurement

As of January 2018, this initiative has recognized over 6000 start-ups and has already funded 99. Furthermore, as of January 2018, 74 start-ups have been approved for tax benefits. In addition, “Start-up India hub” was operationalized on April 1, 2016, and it has handled over 77,000 start-ups and the initiative related queries. It has mentored close to 500 start-ups pertaining to incubation, business plan, revenue model and funding support.

A list of key initiatives and programs undertaken by the GOI are below:

Scheme	Key incentive
Atal Tinkering Laboratories	Grant-in-aid, that includes Rs 10 lakhs as establishment cost and Rs 10 lakhs for operational expenses
Biotechnology Industry Partnership Programme	Support for innovative technologies
Atal Incubation Centres	Grant-in-aid of Rs 10 Crore to each incubation centre
SPARSH (Social Innovation programme for Products: Affordable & Relevant to Societal Health)	Loan

Promoting Innovations in Individuals, Start-ups and MSMEs (PRISM)	Support grant
Rapid Grant for Young Investigator (RGYI)	Grants to young entrepreneurs
National Clean Energy Fund (NCEF) Refinance	Refinance amount up to RS 15 Cr per project.
Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY)	Loan support up to Rs 10 lakhs
Single Point Registration Scheme (SPRS)	Exemption from payment of Earnest Money Deposit (EMD)
NewGen Innovation and Entrepreneurship Development Centre (NewGen IEDC)	One-time financial assistance of upto Rs 25 lakhs
Technology Development Programme (TDP)	Financial support for staff, equipment, and supplies
SIDBI Make in India Soft Loan Fund for Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (SMILE)	Loan support
Stand Up India	Loan support between 10 Lakhs and INR 1 Cr
Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY)	Skill Certification

In addition, the initiatives like Make in India that aimed to make India a global manufacturing hub are estimated to serve as crucial drivers for the entire start-up ecosystem in India as well. With the increasing stature of India in the area of ease of doing business, and increased transparency pertaining to bureaucracy is expected to impact the start-up scene in a positive manner. Similarly, Atal Innovation Mission (AIM) is one such initiative to promote an environment of innovation and entrepreneurship. Furthermore, Digital India aims to make the consumption of government services streamlined and through electronic means and make India digitally-empowered. One of the key GOI initiatives in 2017 was the Start-up India Learning program. In addition, start-ups were allowed to secure 100% of their funding from Foreign Venture Capital Investors (FVCI).

From the perspective of corporate initiatives, YES Bank launched its accelerator in 2017. In addition, Apple launched its app accelerator in India as well. Furthermore, along with Bosch, Philips announced its corporate fund to support start-ups in India as well

Difficulties faced by start-ups in availing government start-up policy benefits

Apart from the usual challenges as mentioned in the graph2 analysis, start-ups are also facing issues in availing government facilities which are offered as part of “start-up India initiative”. It is almost two years now since start-up India initiative has been brought into action but the program is yet to make a major impact on its many promises. It is seen that only a handful of start-ups have been included in the program till today. According to a research conducted by Tracxn, in the last 12 months since the Start-up India policy was initiated, 522 out of about 1425 companies have been certified by the government to avail its benefits.

As the health-tech start-ups are increasing every year, there is very little support extended by the government of India in addressing issues faced by these start-ups. Out of 125 incubation centres announced across the country under the start-up India policy, there are only around 12 incubation centres are dedicated to developing healthcare technologies. Government is also experiencing a delay in making use of its Fund of Funds initiative where it is supposed to deploy 10,000 crores by 2015 through Small Industries Development Bank of India. Due to its slow and complicated process involved in the India start-up policy, this amount has reached a very small number of start-ups to date.

Company	Inception	Idea	Difficulty faced
Loan Tap	2016	Loan lending platform for salaried professionals	Could not find an incubator that specialises in financial technology to certify their company as innovative

Table2: Difficulties in availing GOI start-up policy

Some of the other difficulties faced by companies are

1. Companies have to furnish a letter of recommendation from government approved incubators
2. Getting a letter of recommendation is time-consuming
3. A Lot of documentation is involved in start-up registration despite the digital processes that the government promised during the launch
4. Start-up policy’s extensive list of selection criteria has discouraged many good start-ups in not getting registered under this policy

Other challenges faced by start-ups

According to YS research and Inc42 research, there were more than 500 start-ups that shut down in 2017. Some of the closed start-ups which were officially identified include Task Bob, Stayzilla, Yumist, Tolexo, Finomena, EatFresh, Cardback, Propheese, Shopo and more. Some of these start-ups had attracted decent funding and also they were able to attract customers but were still not able to survive.

According to a study conducted by the IBM Institute of business value in collaboration with Oxford Economics, more than 90% start-ups in India fail in their first five years. The study also revealed following failure reasons,

1. **Lack of Innovation:** As Indian start-ups are used to imitate already successful global ideas, they lack pioneering innovation in their business
2. **Lack of skilled workforce:** The research by IBM surprisingly reveals that finding talents is one of the biggest challenges faced by Indian start-ups.
3. Other reasons include **poor business ethics, inadequate formal mentoring, and lack of experienced leadership**

Another recent report published by NASSCOM in 2017 further reveals that nearly 25% of Indian start-ups which have been incepted between 2012 and 2017 are closed for the following reasons

Graph1: Start-up death rate analysis by NASSCOM

Note: **Scalability related issue**- Failure to scale business, low market demand and sales, strong competition; **external factors**- government norms, regulations

According to NASSCOM report majority of the start-ups have failed to scale-up their business due to low market demand and low sales facing strong competition from other firms. Lack of funding is also one of the major reasons identified for the failure of start-ups in India.

Failed start-up cases

Company	Inception	Idea	Shutdown Reason
GoZoomo	2014	Mobile-based peer-to-peer platform for user car transactions that helps the patrons to buy verified, pre-inspected cars directly from owners without paying any brokerage	Difficulties in achieving unit economics with market difficulties in sales
PepperTap	2014	Online local grocery delivery service	Lack of demand and poor unit economics
askme.com	2010	Consumer internet search platform	Lack of funds
Bonafide softwares pvt ltd	2013	School ERP solution provider	Lack of coordination between top management executives
Muziboo	2007	Online community for music creators	Received a number of Digital millennium copyright act notices from different labels
TaskBob	2014	Facilitates instant, high-quality home services for customers while driving higher productivity for servicemen	Unable to reach desired scale and profit
Rooms Tonight	2014	Hotel booking start-up	Unable to raise funds
Cardback	2012	Payment recommendation platform that helps credit, debit, prepaid cardholders save decent bucks every time they pay	Inability to raise funds and lack of demand
Turant delivery	2015	Platform to help customers book and monitor their deliveries on a daily basis	High cash crunch and unable to raise funds
Parcelled.in	2014	On-demand logistic service provider	Poor margin and high cash crunch
Tolexo	2015	Online marketplace for business goods and supplies	Dip in sales
Stayzilla	2005	Hotel aggregator	Lack of local network, inability to expand
Prophesee	2014	SaaS platform to compare and analyse digital campaigns	Lack of funding
Eatonomist	2014	Food tech	Losses, competition, and Lack of funding
Shopo	2015	Online marketplace	Losses and lack of funding
Fashionara	2012	E-commerce platform for apparel, footwear etc.	Investor exit, lack of funding
AutoRaja	2013	auto rickshaw aggregator	lack of funding
FranklyMe	2014	platform for micro-blogging using videos	No sustainable product-market fit
Tooler	2015	On-demand laundry	Lack of funds
Zippon	2015	packing and moving service	Lack of funds
Purple	2013	Ed-tech	Cash burn and dip in sales

Company	Inception	Idea	Shutdown Reason
Fabfurnish	2011	Online shopping destination for furniture and homeware	Management problem
Finomena	2015	Facilitate small-ticket loans to students and young professionals for buying electronic devices and appliances	Lack of funding
HotelsAroundYou	2013	Last minute hotel booking platform	Funding crunch and the inability to raise the follow-up round after the seed funding round
InksEdge	2014	Used to run an online portal for stationery and personalised cards	Cash crunch and inability to raise the follow-on funding round.
Overcart	2007	E-commerce marketplace for over-stock, unboxed, refurbished, and pre-owned products	The dissatisfied consumers and the overall low product quality
Roder	2014	Inter-city on-demand cabs	Due to rising customer acquisition costs
Yumist	2015	Serve home-style cooked meals prepared in its own kitchen	Lack of proper business model
Kaaryah	2014	Technology-enabled and data analytics-driven apparel brand that catered to women's western wear category in India	Lack of funding
EatFresh	2012	Marketplace offering Indian and international cuisine on a daily rotating menu prepared by top chefs	For higher profit in other divisions
ShotPitch	2014	Discovery and pitching mobile platforms	Legal complication

Table1: Start-up death rate analysis

Graph2: Start-up death rate analysis

Note: **Scalability related issue**- Failure to scale business, low market demand and sales, strong competition; **other reason**- Legal complication

As India develops and the Indian consumer evolves, the primary reason for the failure of start-ups in the country has been constantly changing. One of the main reasons for a start-up to fail was the lack of proper funding and the bearish attitude of the investors in India. However, in 2017, it is the lack of proper targeting of the product/service, a fragile business model, and failure to solve an actual problem that the consumer faces. This eventually leads to a dip in sales and profitability. In addition, the advent of copycats and barrage of start-ups with undifferentiated product and service offerings eventually leads to a price war that affects profitability and increases the failure rate of start-ups. These factors add up to hinder further funding of these start-ups as investors increasingly develop a pessimistic attitude regarding the chances of these start-ups. As such, funding remains one of the crucial issues as more than a quarter of start-ups face problems to raise funds beyond the Series-A funding stage.

The overcrowded start-up scene solving similar problems is one of the key reasons for the dampening profitability of the start-ups in India and their failure in the subsequent funding rounds and eventual shutdown. After the initial success of the pioneering Flipkart, the awareness for e-commerce in the country increased exponentially and it garnered a lot of attention, which led to the advent of a slew of start-ups such as Jabong, Myntra, and Shopclues. Most of these start-ups neither had the resources nor the brand equity to compete with Flipkart in the already occupied market with various cash heavy competitors such as Snapdeal, which eventually led to their demise. The small start-ups cannot burn cash like the large ones like Flipkart and survive tough times. And when the cash-heavy behemoth Amazon arrived in the Indian landscape, the situation turned for the worse.

For instance, the food delivery sector is overcrowded and has key players like Zomato, Swiggy, Food Panda, and Toungestun, along with the dedicated applications of the food outlets. The impending advent of Ola and Uber into these sectors is expected to further amplify the competition and only the cash-burning large start-ups are expected to survive in the long run.

One of the primary problems in India is the lack of true innovation in terms of business model. Even the FlipKart and the OLA Cabs, regarded as the shining jewels of the Indian start-up ecosystem can be considered to be copycat business models of their foreign peers. The mentality is basically if something works, people try to play safe and implement the same idea because the market viability of the idea is already proved and is never brought into question by the potential investors. As such, funding becomes comparatively easier.

The year 2017 was a lacklustre year for Indian start-ups with the impact of GST and demonetization continued to be felt across the start-up landscape.

Conclusion

The brief analysis of the current start-up ecosystem in India has clarified that there is no dearth of support and empowerment for start-ups in India, from the government as well as from the private sector. There are more than 50 schemes and initiatives with the end goal of enabling and driving the start-up ecosystem in the country. India is among the top three countries in the world in terms of the number of start-ups and has a host of successful start-ups such as Ola, Flipkart, Paytm, InMobi, Zomato, and Quikr. However, the dissemination of benefits proposed by these initiatives across Tier-2 cities, and the actual ground level implementation of these policies remain a concern for the start-up ecosystem in India. Even with policies and initiatives in place, the Indian bureaucracy mind-set and lack of a proactive attitude have eventually dampened the overall effect of these positive schemes and initiatives. The primary problem has been inefficient, disorganized and unsystematic fund deployment, leading to many start-ups failing due to lack of funds. As the tech-driven and innovative start-ups lack to get any effective funding support, the comparatively safer investment such as the traditional businesses continue to secure funding. As such, the government needs to ease up its selection criteria to recognize startups that may be non-traditional and hence risky, so as to promote a culture of innovation and out-of-the-box thinking, rather than copycat competitors. This brief analysis makes it apparent that the government has to change its stance towards the start-ups and adopt a more hands-on role. Indian start-ups need further institutional and governmental assistance to meet their business requirements such as easy and fast registration, timely funding and mentoring from successful entrepreneurs.

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